

The Use of the Podomoro Technique in Improving the Results of Listening and Speaking Class Evaluation

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ABSTRACT: The suitability of using teaching tools or materials in teaching is essential to achieve what students want and the learning objectives. Not only are the right and appropriate teaching tools or materials needed, but teaching and learning methods that are appropriate to what students need are also needed. Students can use the Podomoro technique to focus more on studying the materials. Not only that, but efficiency in the use of time can also help students to be more focused on studying what is being studied. This research is quantitative. The design is a one-group pretest-posttest. The Pretest and Posttest scores were analyzed using the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test, which was implemented using a statistical application called SPSS. There are different results from the three different classes for the Listening and Speaking classes, which show that the Podomoro technique helps learning outcomes. Statistically significant improvement was observed in two classes ($p = 0.005$ and $p = 0.016$), but not in the third ($p = 0.388$).

KEYWORDS: Evaluation, Podomoro technique, One-group pretest-posttest, Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test

INTRODUCTION

The development of technology is currently growing very rapidly. Many previously difficult or impossible things have now become possible or can be done and are also easier. Many things have been helped by the development of technology today in terms of communication. It was previously difficult to communicate face-to-face, only to be able to listen to voices. It can happen with ZOOM and various applications that support face-to-face conversations. Unfortunately, the same thing does not happen in the world of education. Education does not develop like technology; there are still many things related to education that are not as easy as technology.

“Although this transformation offers many opportunities, such as wider and more flexible access to education, it also presents various challenges that need to be overcome, both in terms of infrastructure, teaching quality, and the readiness of students and educators themselves” (mtsn8sleman, 2025). It is true that with the development of technology, access to education and implementation have become easier. Education does not have to be carried out in the classroom, but can be done via a computer or laptop screen. However, many things still cannot be solved with technology in education. Infrastructure, quality of teaching, whether or not students are ready to learn, and educators’ unpreparedness in teaching.

Teaching and learning methods are not necessarily updated with the rapid development of technology. Many existing or developing methods are still limited to teaching with one-way communication. The existing teaching methods only drain students’ energy in learning, not helping students not to experience fatigue in the learning process. “The use of artificial intelligence in personalizing learning, augmented reality, and virtual reality to help the learning experience, as well as the use of simulations and educational games, are part of innovative learning methods in society 5.0” (Yessi, 2021). Current technological developments are more about how to experience teaching and learning in other forms and use media to support the teaching and learning process. This can be seen from the developments in Society 5.0.

Even in courses, technology does not necessarily help in overcoming deficiencies or difficulties in the form of learning methods that can indeed be more helpful, only in the form of infrastructure; of course, the need for the internet is very much needed to support the teaching process of courses that use technology. One is learning English, which requires direct interaction in understanding the material, which cannot necessarily be met with current technology.

“Of course, the principle of modern technology integration in the classroom does not mainly give the learners some chances to experience another method of learning, but rather the ultimate goal is to encourage and motivate the learners to actively engage in the learning process (Rintaningrum, 2023). From the quote from Rintaningrum’s article, it is clear that today’s modern

technology, combined with the learning process, does not give students a taste of new methods, only methods that use applications offered by the internet. That is why new methods can anticipate student conditions so that they are always ready to learn without getting tired, especially in courses with many credits. Specifically, this study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. How does the Pomodoro learning method help students with their learning outcomes?
2. How does the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test evaluate student learning outcomes?

This study holds significance as it provides new perspectives on the Pomodoro technique learning method in improving students' learning outcomes in listening and speaking classes. The Pomodoro technique learning method is an area that has been underexplored in listening and speaking classes within previous research. Employing the Pomodoro technique learning method enhances the understanding in the listening and speaking class. Moreover, the findings contribute to the broader field of English learning, especially in listening and speaking English. It is also supporting a new way to evaluate students' learning outcomes by using the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Learning English, which should be given through direct interaction, consists of 4 main things that must be learned: listening, speaking, writing, and reading. "Mastering the four aspects of English (speaking, writing, listening, and reading) is the key to fluency in English. These four aspects complement each other, helping us communicate effectively in various situations." (PasarTrainer Blog, 2024). Many courses are studied to cover the four aspects above. One of the courses that can cover the four aspects above is the Listening and Speaking and Reading and Writing courses. Of the two courses, the one that requires direct interaction in its teaching is Listening and Speaking.

Listening and speaking is a course that requires direct interaction to understand the language spoken and heard more easily. "Listening skill is the ability to identify the language and understand the meaning of what speakers are saying. Understanding a meaning is hardly easy to do unless she/he has a strong listening skill" (Saehu, 2016). "About listening skills, one of the skills considered an important skill for learning language, specifically for communicating, is speaking...People cannot turn out a word correctly, especially non-native speakers, without listening to someone first, or on the other hand, before being a good listener, they cannot be a good speaker" (Nathania, 2024).

Listening is the ability to identify what language is used and what the speaker wants to convey to the listener. It is not easy to understand what is heard if the listener does not have good listening skills, especially if the language differs from their mother tongue. Speaking is an ability that is closely related to Listening. That is why, in learning English, good listening and speaking skills are essential. A person will not be able to speak well if they do not have good listening skills. Someone cannot communicate correctly if they do not first listen to what others are saying. That is why speaking skills are closely related to listening skills.

In addition to being closely related to speaking and listening skills, good speaking skills can provide many benefits. "Speaking is a beneficial language skill that enables speakers and listeners to interact orally for information transfer, connection building, and sharing. One such language with a need on a global scale for learners at all levels of communication is English" (Ork et al., 2024). With good speaking skills, speakers can communicate with listeners. From the communication process, the speaker and listener will feel many benefits. These benefits include exchanging information, building good connections or relationships, and sharing in matters related to what is communicated. Moreover, when someone wants to develop all of that internationally, mastering English is very much needed in speaking and listening.

Improving speaking and listening skills is essential because of the great benefits of mastering English. One way that teachers need to apply in helping to teach these things is to understand what needs to be used to support teaching. "..., there is a need for improvement from the teacher to choose the right teaching tools and learning designs that can meet the learning needs of students so that listening learning achievements can be appropriately achieved" (Utami et al., 2023).

The suitability of using teaching tools or materials in teaching is essential to achieve what students want and the learning objectives. Not only are the right and appropriate teaching tools or materials needed, but teaching and learning methods that are appropriate to what students need are also needed. That is why teachers are required to be able to develop themselves in teaching and also understand what students need in terms of teaching tools or materials and teaching and learning methods. "Methods are techniques or tools for delivering material by paying attention to student needs to help maximize learning process activities" (Bastomi et al., 2022).

“...in the learning process in elementary schools still faces several challenges. One of the biggest challenges is the limited learning models that are effective...” (Munjiah et al., 2024). Until now, learning methods have been a significant problem in education. Munjiah said in her article that learning in elementary schools still has problems in the learning process, and appropriate learning methods are still one of the main topics, not only in elementary schools but also in various levels of education, including higher education. The suitability of teaching and learning methods that suit the needs of students is needed. The increasingly high credit load will drain students’ energy in the learning process and understand the material presented.

There must be a distinction between studying hard and studying smart in working and learning. Studying hard is not always necessary, but studying smart is also necessary, especially if the number of hours required to study requires a prolonged duration. “In learning, there are terms of hard study and smart study. The hard study is studying without knowing the time, while the smart study is studying by utilizing time efficiency.

Of course, it is not recommended for students to apply hard study. So, the Pomodoro technique is a smart study technique” (Ariviani et al., 2015). Ariviani et al. distinguish hard study from tireless study. Even though the time is extended, the tiredness must be overcome. At the same time, smart study is learning to utilize the available time. Not only that but making time efficient is also necessary for implementing the smart study. Ariviani et al. believe that the Pomodoro technique is one of the innovative study techniques.

The Pomodoro technique is innovative, considering the learning outcomes obtained from the time used. “The Pomodoro technique is a time management technique developed by Francesco Cirillo in 1980. According to Francesco, the Pomodoro technique was created to empower the time we use and increase learning productivity” (Afiah et al., 2024). The Pomodoro technique was developed by Francesco Cirillo in 1980. Francesco sees the technique as a technique that regulates the time used. Not utilizing the available time to continue learning but more on managing the available time so that the learning process becomes more effective and productive for teachers and students.

In addition to what Afiah et al. said in their article about the inventor of the Pomodoro technique, Kisno also provided additional information regarding understanding the Pomodoro technique. “Kisno (2020) added that the Pomodoro technique is a learning technique for managing time or the term time management, which can help someone work focused in the time they have” (Bastomi et al., 2022). In their article, Bastomi et al. quoted what Kisno wrote, which states that the Pomodoro technique is a technique that manages the available time so that people who are given that time to do something can stay focused on doing it.

When connected to the learning process, the Pomodoro technique is used to manage study time so that students stay focused on their learning process. This is also in line with what Kusmiati et al. said in their article. “With the Pomodoro learning method, students can manage the desired time so that study time becomes more focused and efficient” (Kusmiati et al., 2024). Kusmiati et al. stated that students can use the Pomodoro technique to focus more on studying the materials. Not only that, efficiency in the use of time can also help students to be more focused on studying what is being studied.

“Francesco Cirillo began to change his learning mechanism with certain time intervals to maintain his physical and mental condition. He divided his study and rest time efficiently” (Nasution et al., 2022). In applying the Pomodoro technique, Nasution et al. stated in their article that using the Pomodoro technique focused on the time interval when studying. This is done to maintain students’ physical and mental condition so they can be maintained properly without feeling tired in the learning process.

The interval here is intended to divide study and rest time. For example, 100 minutes is the duration of studying a course; it can be divided into study and rest time. The first 20 minutes are used for studying, and then the first 5 minutes are used for rest, and then continue to the second 20 minutes for studying and practicing the next 5 for rest. The remaining 10 minutes are used to close the learning or lecture. This division of time in the Pomodoro technique is believed to help students and teachers go through the teaching and learning process more refreshed without feeling stressed by the long learning process.

After the learning process is completed a series of times, the next thing teachers must do is evaluate the results obtained from the students. “In the education system, learning evaluation has a crucial role in ensuring the effectiveness and quality of the learning process” (Sunaryati et al., 2024). Sunaryati et al. stated in their article that learning evaluation is crucial in seeing whether what has been implemented is effective or needs to be changed later.

This evaluation can also be used to see whether the students fully understand the materials that have been taught, or only a few or even a small part understand. That is why the evaluation process in the education system is critical and must align with what Saputra said in his article. “Learning evaluation is an important aspect of the learning process. By conducting learning evaluations,

lecturers can find out the level of success of the delivery of material carried out during teaching and learning activities” (Saputra, 2023). From this evaluation process, teachers can assess the level of success of the material that has been delivered. By seeing how many students get good to excellent grades, teachers can decide whether the method applied to the learning process is successful.

“In the world of education, data-based evaluation is becoming an increasingly important tool in efforts with the quality of education and learning (Marques Queiroga et al., 2024)” (Febrianita et al., 2025). Febrianita et al. stated that currently, the most appropriate and valid form of evaluation is evaluation in the form of data. From this data, teachers can use it for the administration process. This data is in the form of grades and descriptions of student performance during the learning process. With this data, teachers can compare later, at which time the implementation of the teaching pattern is considered the best from the many data created by teachers. This is what is called evaluation.

One that can be used as a test tool from existing data from the learning process to make an evaluation is the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test. “The Wilcoxon signed rank modification test functions to test differences between paired data, test comparisons between observations before and after (before after) treatment is given and determine the effectiveness of a treatment” (Windi et al., 2021). This Wilcoxon test compares differences in data that are indeed a series of processes.

With this test, a comparison process can be carried out from the beginning of the observation to after the application is carried out. From this comparison, it will be possible to see and determine whether or not the treatment that has been given is adequate. “The Wilcoxon signed rank test also measures the distance or magnitude of the difference for pairs of data values” (Fadilatunnisyah et al., 2024). Fadilatunnisyah et al. also mentioned in their article that the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test is used to find out how big the difference is from pairs of data containing values that have been created previously. The results obtained can be used to decide on the treatment given. “In the Wilcoxon signed rank test, variables are compared between abnormal returns before and after treatment is given” (Rahmalia et al., 2020).

Wilcoxon is usually used after an initial test before treatment and a final test after treatment is given. “Based on the results of the Wilcoxon Signed Rank test on the pretest and posttest values of patient safety target training, it was found that there was a difference between the pretest conducted before the training intervention and the posttest” (Dhamanti et al., 2022). The article by Dhamanti et al. stated that they used the Wilcoxon test to compare the pretest with the posttest. This was done to determine whether the patient safety target training could be considered effective or beneficial or whether it should not have been necessary. From the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test, it can be assessed whether the previous assumptions were proven or not. “Testing the hypothesis, statistical analysis is used with the Wilcoxon rank test formula” (Lestari et al., 2023). Lestari et al. stated in their article that the Wilcoxon test can be used to answer the hypothesis made by a researcher in their research report and is generally used in statistical calculations. Researchers will later use the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test to evaluate the pretest and posttest that have been obtained previously. The Podomoro technique treatment will be given after the pretest results are obtained. The results obtained from the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test calculation are used to answer the hypothesis regarding the Podomoro technique.

METHODS

This research is quantitative. “Quantitative research is an investigation of social problems based on testing a theory consisting of variables, measured by numbers, and analyzed by statistical procedures to determine whether the predictive generalization of the theory is correct” (Ali et al., 2022). Measurement in quantitative research is identical to using numbers, which are later analyzed using a counting tool according to statistical procedures. Quantitative methods are used when testing a theory or applying a theory to examine the success or effectiveness of the theory in a situation.

The design used is a one-group pretest-posttest. One-Group Pretest-Posttest Design is a type of learning that must be observed before and after treatment is given” (Noviyanti et al., 2023). According to Noviyanti et al.’s article, the One Group Pretest-Posttest design is a research design regarding observations of a treatment given to one group used as a research subject.

The study subjects were UNDIRA (Dian Nusantara University) students in the 2022/2023 academic year. These students were treated in the Listening and Speaking two-course according to one of the abovementioned theories. These students were treated in the Listening and Speaking two-course according to one of the abovementioned theories.

The pretest was conducted after the start of the lecture until before the mid-test period, when the treatment had not been applied. The pretest is the mid-test score. The posttest was conducted after the mid-test, and when the treatment would be applied. The

treatment period occurred from the meeting after the mid-test until before the final test. The posttest is the final test score. The Pretest and Posttest scores were analyzed using the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test, which was implemented using a statistical application called SPSS. This test measures the interval of difference between the Pretest and Posttest. The results of this interval will be used to answer whether the Podomoro technique was effective in the Listening and Speaking course's learning situation

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

This analysis uses aggregated, non-identifiable academic grade information system output for descriptive reporting of student performance; no individual-level student data is accessed.

RESULT

The Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test (nonparametric test) is a statistical test used by researchers to calculate results and perform other functions. "Non-parametric statistics are statistical formulas used when the sample taken is likely to be relatively small. It is also used to analyze data from test results, questionnaires, or other data collection instruments designed to ensure ideas and research results, regardless of whether the data is normal or not" (Zulkipli et al., 2024).

The researcher chose to use the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test in evaluating the pretest and posttest of the applied treatment, the Podomoro technique, because the number of students was less than 30. The researcher taught several Listening and speaking classes and selected several to test the research hypothesis and determine its appropriateness.

Below is a list of Listening and Speaking IV class scores, using the UTS score as a pretest and the UAS score as a posttest score

Table 1. Table of scores Listening and Speaking IV

No	Participants	Mid-term exam	Final Exam	Mean
1	Participant 1	47	74,6	60,8
2	Participant 2	20	67,6	57,3
3	Participant 3	30	68,2	57,6
4	Participant 4	60	73	66,5
5	Participant 5	45	70	57,5
6	Participant 6	52	71,2	61,6
7	Participant 7	73	80	76,5
8	Participant 8	40	68,2	54,1
9	Participant 9	63	73,6	68,3
10	Participant 10	53	69,2	61,1

From the list of values above, it can be seen that the class has only 10 students. In terms of percentage, the increase shows that all students experienced an increase from the mid-term exam score to the final exam score. In this Excel calculation, it can be seen that all scores increased, not decreased.

After getting the mid-term exam (pretest) and final exam (posttest) scores, the researcher began to calculate using the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test to determine whether there was a difference between the two tests, as well as to answer whether the hypothesis of using the Podomoro technique helped increase scores or not.

Table 2. Table of Ranks Listening and Speaking IV

Ranks		N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
Post test - Pre test	Negative Ranks	0 ^a	.00	.00
	Positive Ranks	10 ^b	5.50	55.00
	Ties	0 ^c		
	Total	10		

a. Post test < Pre test

b. Post test > Pre test

c. Post test = Pre test

From the Ranks output above, several things are concluded, including:

1. Negative ranks, or the difference (negative) between learning outcomes using the Podomoro technique for Listening and Speaking class IV, are 0, both in the N value, Mean Rank, or Sum of Ranks. This means that there is no decrease (reduction) from the mid-term exam (pretest) value to the final exam (posttest) value.
2. Positive Ranks or the difference (positive) between learning outcomes using the Podomoro technique Listening and Speaking class IV technique. Here, there are 10 positive data points (N), which means that the 10 students experienced an increase in learning outcomes in the Listening and Speaking IV course from the mid-term exam (pretest) value to the final exam (posttest) value. The mean rank or average increase is 5.50, while the number of positive ranks or Sum of Ranks is 55.00.
3. Ties are the similarity of the mid-term exam (pretest) and final exam (posttest) values. The Ties value here is 0, so it can be concluded that there are no equal values between the mid-term exam (pretest) and the final exam (posttest).

Next, to test the hypothesis, the researcher used the second output from the SPSS calculation results, the Test Statistics output. The following will describe the basis for decision-making used in the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test as a guideline. The basis for decision-making in the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test:

1. "If Asymp.sig value (2-tailed) is smaller than <0.05, Ha is accepted
2. If Asymp.sig value (2-tailed) is bigger than >0.05, Ha is rejected." (Sianipar, 2022)

Table 3. Table of Test Statistics Listening and Speaking IV

Test Statistics ^a	
	Post test - Pre test
Z	-2.803 ^b
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.005

a. Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test

b. Based on negative ranks.

Based on the Test Statistics output above, it is known that Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) is 0.005. Because 0.005 is smaller than 0.05, it can be concluded that Ha is accepted. With this, there is a difference between learning outcomes using the Podomoro technique for the mid-term exam (pretest) and final exam (posttest). Thus, using the Podomoro technique as a teaching and learning technique in the classroom affects the learning outcomes of English and Listening IV classes.

Then, the researcher re-tested the learning outcomes using the Wilcoxon Signed Rank test in another Listening and Speaking class, which the researcher had taught using the Podomoro technique. The aim was to see whether this application applies equally in different situations.

The following list of scores is a list of scores from the Listening and Speaking II class. The researcher taught this class at a different time from the previous class. The researcher again used UTS as the pretest score and UAS as the posttest score.

Table 4. Table of list of scores English and Speaking II

No	Participants	Mid-term exam	Final Exam	Mean
1	Participant 1	0	0	0
2	Participant 2	20	83	51,5
3	Participant 3	58,3	85	71,65
4	Participant 4	0	0	0
5	Participant 5	58,3	85	71,65
6	Participant 6	73,3	85	79,15
7	Participant 7	86,6	85	85,8
8	Participant 8	70	85	77,5
9	Participant 9	93,3	85	89,15
10	Participant 10	53,3	83	68,15
11	Participant 11	91,6	85	88,3
12	Participant 12	61,6	85	73,3
13	Participant 13	0	0	0
14	Participant 14	60	80	70

The list of values above shows that the number of students in the class is also small, totaling 14. In terms of percentage, the increase is not all students experienced an increase from the mid-term exam score to the final exam score. Some even experienced a decrease in their increase, meaning that the student did not experience an increase but a decrease.

There are also some students whose percentage is not read because their score is only recorded as 0. These students got such scores because they did not take the midterm and final exams. This Excel calculation shows that not all scores increased; some were not read because their scores remained the same, and some also decreased.

After getting the mid-term exam (pretest) and final exam (posttest) scores, the researcher began to calculate using the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test to determine whether there was a difference between the two tests, as well as to answer whether the hypothesis of using the Podomoro technique also helped increase scores or not when tested in the class.

Table 5. Table 1 Table of Ranks Listening and Speaking II

Ranks		N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
Post test - Pre test	Negative Ranks	3 ^a	2.00	6.00
	Positive Ranks	8 ^b	7.50	60.00
	Ties	3 ^c		
	Total	14		

a. Post test < Pre test

b. Post test > Pre test

c. Post test = Pre test

From the Ranks output above, several things are concluded, including:

1. Negative ranks or the difference (negative) between learning outcomes using the Podomoro technique for the Listening and Speaking II class is 3 in the N value, 2.00 in the Mean Rank, and 6.00 in the Sum of Ranks. This means that there is a decrease (reduction) from the mid-term exam (pretest) score to the final exam (posttest) score experienced by three students.
2. Positive Ranks or the difference (positive) between learning outcomes using the Podomoro technique for the Listening and Speaking II class. Here, there are eight positive data (N), which means that eight students experienced an increase in learning outcomes in the Listening and Speaking IV course from the mid-term exam (pretest) score to the final exam (posttest) score.

The mean rank or average increase is 7.50, while the number of positive ranks or Sum of Ranks is 60.00.

3. Ties are the similarity of the mid-term exam (pretest) and final exam (posttest) scores. The Ties value here is 3, so it can be concluded that three students have the same score between the mid-term exam (pretest) and the final exam (posttest).

Next, to test the hypothesis, the researcher used the second output from the SPSS calculation results, the Test Statistics output. The following will describe the basis for decision-making used in the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test as a guideline. The basis for decision-making in the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test:

1. "If Asymp.sig value (2-tailed) is smaller than <0.05 , H_a is accepted
2. If Asymp.sig value (2-tailed) is bigger than >0.05 , H_a is rejected." (Sianipar, 2022)

Table 6. Table of Test Statistics Listening and Speaking II

Test Statistics ^a	
	Post test - Pre test
Z	-2.402 ^b
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.016

a. Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test

b. Based on negative ranks.

Based on the Test Statistics output above, it is known that Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) is 0.016. Because 0.016 is smaller than 0.05, it can be concluded that H_a is accepted. This means there is a difference between the learning outcomes using the Podomoro technique for the mid-term exam (pretest) and the final exam (posttest). Thus, using the Podomoro technique as a teaching and learning technique in the classroom helps the learning outcomes of the English and Listening II classes.

Furthermore, the researcher re-tested the learning outcomes using the Wilcoxon Signed Rank test in other Listening and Speaking classes, which the researcher had taught using the Podomoro technique. The aim was to see whether this application applied the same in the classroom situation.

The following list of scores is a list of scores from the Listening and Speaking I class. The researcher taught this class at a different time from the previous class. The researcher again used the mid-term exam as the pretest score and the final exam as the posttest score.

Table 7. Table of list of scores English and Speaking I

No	Participants	Mid-term exam	Final Exam	Mean
1	Participant 1	88	92	90
2	Participant 2	70	60	65
3	Participant 3	75	60	67,5
4	Participant 4	60	86	73
5	Participant 5	0	0	0
6	Participant 6	65	55	60
7	Participant 7	51	69	60
8	Participant 8	76	60	68
9	Participant 9	84	55	69,5
10	Participant 10	73	55	64
11	Participant 11	62	83	72,5
12	Participant 12	86	60	73
13	Participant 13	70	61	65,5
14	Participant 14	0	0	0

The list of values above shows that the number of students in the class is also small, totaling 14 students. In terms of percentage, it can be seen that not all students experienced an increase from mid-term to final exams. Quite a lot experienced a minus in their increase, meaning that the students did not experience an increase but a decrease.

There are also some students whose percentage is not readable because their scores are only recorded as 0. These students got scores like that because they did not take the midterm and final exams. This Excel calculation shows that not all scores increased; some were not readable because their scores remained the same, and some also decreased. The majority experienced a negative percentage.

After getting the mid-term exam (pretest) and final exam (posttest) scores, the researcher began to calculate using the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test to determine whether there was a difference between the two tests, as well as to answer whether the hypothesis of using the Podomoro technique also helped increase scores or not when tested in the class

Table 8. Table of Ranks Listening and Speaking I

Ranks		N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
Post test - Pre test	Negative Ranks	8 ^a	6.25	50.00
	Positive Ranks	4 ^b	7.00	28.00
	Ties	2 ^c		
	Total	14		

a. Post test < Pre test

b. Post test > Pre test

c. Post test = Pre test

From the Ranks output above, several things are concluded, including:

1. Negative ranks or the difference (negative) between learning outcomes using the Podomoro technique for the Listening and Speaking II class is 8 in the N value, 6.25 in the Mean Rank, and 50.00 in the Sum of Ranks. This means that there is a decrease (reduction) from the mid-term exam (pretest) score to the final exam (posttest) score experienced by eight students.
2. Positive Ranks or the difference (positive) between learning outcomes using the Podomoro technique for the Listening and Speaking II class. Here, there are four positive data (N), which means that four students experienced an increase in learning outcomes in the Listening and Speaking IV course from the mid-term exam (pretest) score to the final exam (posttest) score. The mean rank or average increase is 7.00, while the number of positive ranks or Sum of Ranks is 28.00.
3. Ties are the similarity of the mid-term exam (pretest) and final exam (posttest) scores. The Ties value here is 2, so it can be concluded that two students have the same score between the mid-term exam (pretest) and the final exam (posttest).

Next, to test the hypothesis, the researcher used the second output from the SPSS calculation results, the Test Statistics output. The following will describe the basis for decision-making used in the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test as a guideline. The basis for decision-making in the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test:

1. "If Asymp.sig value (2-tailed) is smaller than <0.05, Ha is accepted
2. If Asymp.sig value (2-tailed) is bigger than >0.05, Ha is rejected." (Sianipar, 2022)

Table 9. Table of Test Statistics Listening and Speaking II

Test Statistics ^a	
	Post test - Pre test
Z	-.864 ^b
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.388

a. Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test

b. Based on positive ranks.

Based on the Test Statistics output above, it is known that Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) is 0.388. Because 0.388 is greater than 0.05, it can be concluded that H_a is rejected. This means there is a difference between the learning outcomes using the Podomoro technique for mid-term exam (pretest) and final exam (posttest). Thus, there is no effect of using the Podomoro technique as a teaching and learning technique in the classroom on the learning outcomes of the English and Listening I class.

DISCUSSION

There are different results from the three different classes for the Listening and Speaking classes, which show that the Podomoro technique helps learning outcomes. The Podomoro technique has an overall effect on the Listening and Speaking IV class and the majority of the Listening and Speaking II class. However, in the Listening and Speaking II class, three students got a zero on both tests because these students were not present when the mid-term exam and final exam were carried out. There were also three students whose final exam scores decreased compared to their mid-term exam scores.

For the Listening and Speaking I class, the results of the SPSS calculation are stated in the class; the Podomoro technique does not have an effect, so there is no increase in most learning outcomes. In the class, four students experienced an increase, but eight students experienced a decrease from their mid-term exam score to their final exam score. There are two students whose scores are stable, but this is because the two students were not present during the implementation of the mid-term exam and final exam.

From these results, the Podomoro technique helps student learning outcomes in the Listening and Speaking class group. The Podomoro technique can provide significant results in evaluating learning outcomes. Indeed, from the results of these calculations, there is still one class that is considered unsuccessful in increasing learning outcomes when the Podomoro technique is applied.

This is due to several things, including a lack of focus when working on the exam so that the score decreases, it could also be due to the reluctance of these students to study so that they have difficulty when working on the exam, it could also be because the students are not serious when attending lectures so that they have difficulty in working on the exam

CONCLUSION

Applying the Podomoro technique to three different classes shows that the technique has made these students experience an increase in their learning outcomes. Most students in the three classes experienced an increase in their final exam scores compared to their mid-term exam scores. However, some students still did not experience an increase, and their scores were stable, but this was due to their absence during the two exams or their problems with themselves. Further research must be conducted to determine why it did not work for these students.

The successful implementation of the Podomoro technique can provide a new picture of a teaching method that does not always have to be used all the time. Mental calmness and physical health greatly support students' ability to absorb the material being taught. It is the teacher's job to understand this and help students so that the teaching and learning process is not a tiring specter for them to go through. However, it can be a fun and engaging activity for them to follow. A well-maintained physique can support mental health, while a good mentality can also help physical condition

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